

EFFECTIVENESS OF DEKASAN IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHOLEDOCHOLITHIASIS AND PURULENT CHOLANGITIS

Batirov D.Yu.
Rakhimov A.P.
Yusupov D.D.
Rustamov M.A.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Urgench Branch
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14869488>

Relevance of the Topic:

The incidence of gallstone disease (GD) worldwide has been steadily increasing in recent years [1]. Accordingly, choledocholithiasis, which is the most common complication of GD, is also frequently observed [5]. It often presents asymptotically or without jaundice, while in 15%-47.8% of cases, it is accompanied by purulent cholangitis and jaundice [2,4].

Currently, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the main treatment for GD and its complications. Additionally, various endoscopic procedures are widely used to restore bile duct patency, including endoscopic papillotomy, endoscopic bile duct sanitation and drainage, endoscopic papillosphincteroplasty, balloon dilation, stenting, and others[3]. However, choosing the appropriate treatment method, strategy, and timing for choledocholithiasis and purulent cholangitis remains challenging, particularly in elderly patients and those with comorbidities that significantly increase surgical risks. Therefore, improving treatment outcomes remains a high priority[4].

Objective of the Study:

To improve the surgical treatment outcomes of patients with gallstone disease and its complications, including choledocholithiasis and purulent cholangitis.

Methods and Materials:

A retrospective analysis was conducted on 114 patients diagnosed with GD, choledocholithiasis, and purulent cholangitis who underwent surgical treatment at the surgical departments of the Khorezm Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center from 2012 to 2024. Among them, 54 patients (47.37%) were assigned to the main group, while 60 patients (52.63%) formed the control group.

In the main group, laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed, followed by choledochoscopy through the cystic duct, where bile duct sanitation and stone removal were carried out. The bile ducts were then flushed with a 0.2 mg/mL Dekasan solution heated to 38-40°C. Postoperatively, the bile duct was

continuously irrigated with the same solution via a drainage tube (using the Pikovsky method) for 7-21 days. In the control group (n=60), the same surgical procedure was performed, but the bile ducts were flushed with conventional antiseptic solutions (chlorhexidine, furacilin) and irrigated postoperatively for 8-35 days.

Results:

The postoperative results were as follows:

- Elevated body temperature in the postoperative period was observed in 8 patients (7.02%) in the main group and in 17 patients (14.91%) in the control group.
- The duration of bile duct drainage varied between 7 to 21 days in the main group, while in the control group, some patients required drainage for up to 35 days.
- The average hospital stay in the main group was 5.8 ± 0.27 days, whereas in the control group, it was 7.2 ± 0.31 days.
- Other postoperative outcomes were nearly identical in both groups.

Conclusion:

Flushing the bile ducts with a 0.2 mg/mL Dekasan solution heated to 38-40°C significantly improves treatment outcomes in patients with gallstone disease complicated by choledocholithiasis and purulent cholangitis.

Literature:

1. Aimagambetov M.Zh., Abdrakhmanov S.T. Results of Improving Diagnosis and Optimizing Surgical Treatment of Acute Destructive Calculous Cholecystitis in Patients with Overweight and Obesity. // Science and Healthcare, 2020, Issue 5 (Vol. 22), pp. 100-110.
2. Nazyrov F.G., Akbarov M.M., Saidazimov E.M., Nishanov M.Sh. Errors and Dangers in Biliary Surgery (A Guide for Doctors). // Surgery of Uzbekistan, No. 3, 2020, pp. 58-60.
3. Samsonov A.A., Plotnikova E.Yu., Ruban A.P., Bagmet A.D., Ulyankina E.V., Evdokimova A.I. Gallstone Disease, Cholecystectomy – What’s Next? // Medical Council, No. 4, 2014, pp. 50-54.
4. Khadjibayev A.M., Khadjibayev F.A., Pulatov M.M., Shukurov B.I., Sobitkhanov M.S. The Role of Endobiliary Interventions in the Treatment of Bile Leakage After Cholecystectomy. // Bulletin of Emergency Medicine, 2019, Vol. 12, No. 6, pp. 5-10.
5. Ismailov U.S., Batirov D.Y., Raximov A.P. The Role Of rs1799883 Polymorphism Of The FABP2 Gene In The Pathogenesis Of Nosological Syntropy Of Gallstone Disease And Metabolic Syndrome The American Journal of Medical

Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research (ISSN – 2689-1026) Published: June 18,
2021 | Pages: 46-51 Doi:
<https://doi.org/10.37547/TAJMSPR/Volume03Issue06-07>

